

A survey on data security techniques of steganography

BA20669317 STAVARI ELENI

1. ABSTRACT

Steganography is the practice of concealing information to avoid detection. Steganography is taken from Greek and meaning "covered writing"(1). It is the art of concealing information within digital media and it plays a key role in our current data security. The difference between steganography and cryptography is the part that they concentrate on. Cryptography focuses on encrypting content, whereas steganography wants to hide the existence of the communication itself and in that way minimizing the risk of discovery by adversaries. (2) This survey reviews some data-hiding techniques, putting them in three categories, spatial-domain, transform domain and adaptive approaches (3)(4). It also explores several challenges posed by steganalysis (the process of finding hidden information) and examines new advances in machine learning, particularly generative adversarial networks(GANs) , which shows a promising improvement in the embedding capacity and the detection resistance(5),(6). So this survey aims at providing of an overview of the current data security techniques in steganography, highlighting emerging trends and identifying the challenges of open research.

2. INTRODUCTION

To understand steganography, it is important to understand the difference between it and cryptography. As it was mentioned in the abstract, cryptography focuses on the message, it transforms it into unreadable forms, but it doesn't hide the fact that communication is taking place. Steganography, on the other hand makes it considerably harder for not authorized parties to detect the information by secretly hiding it within harmless carriers (7)(8). This is why steganography is an essential technique for protecting private data, particularly in hostile or censorship- prone settings. Because steganography allows secret communication and data protection is frequently in conjunction with cryptography as essential to contemporary information security (36).

What makes steganography important in data security is the ability to offer a higher level of protection beyond the conventional methods. For achieving this you have to hide the presence of the message, that way the likelihood of interception and suspicion is minimized

and the confidentiality and integrity are enhanced(9) (3). In recent advances the use of GANs (generative adversarial networks) and deep learning is increasing which provides higher payloads and improved resistance against detection.(6) (10)

There is a diversity of applications of steganography, from secure communication channels, to digital watermarking for copyrighting and for data authentication(2)(11)

A new interesting avenue that steganography offers for preventing steganalysis is the appearance of covert image which creates stego images from scratch without altering the cover image.(9)(11). Furthermore, by developing and increasing concealment and security against complex attacks transformer based and deep neural network frameworks significantly advanced steganographic approaches (8)(12). Steganographic solutions that can insert payloads without sacrificing detection resistance or visual quality are becoming even more necessary as digital communication systems are becoming more data intensive. This trend is reflected in recent developments such as compressed sensing-based models which greatly improve embedding, resilience and efficiency (33)

Despite the numerous studies only on steganographic techniques it is still crucial to do a thorough analysis that thta combines both the conventional methods and the machine learning techniques. By examining cutting edge steganography images methods such as deep learning frameworks and spatial and transform domain approaches we can close the “gap” (7)(9)

The focus of this survey is primary on digital image steganography given the research available. Although significant other areas like audio or network steganography are not the scope of this assessment in order to preserve the necessary t clarity and depth

3. BACKGROUND AND FUNDAMENTAL CONCEPTS

KEY TERMINOLOGIES

Understanding a few fundamental terms is essential in the field of steganography. The real secret data that is meant to be hidden is called payload. The file (image, audio, video etc) that is utilized for concealing the payload is known as the carrier or cover of the media. Lastly the object that results from the embedding data into the carrier is referred to as stego-object (13). While extraction is the process of recovering the hidden data from stego-object embedding is the process in reverse, the concealing of the payload into the carrier using specific techniques (14).

TYPES OF STEGANOGRAPHY

The two main ways of steganography is based on carrier and based on the domain that is used for hiding data.

1. By carrier type: steganography can use images, music, video, text even network packets as cover mediums (13). For example image steganography is extensively researched because of the human visual systems ability to tolerate slight distortions which enables efficient data concealment. (15)
2. By Domain: Additionally techniques are categorized into spatial domain and transform domain. Spatial domain are easier to use bu they are also more susceptible to attacks embed information by directly altering pixel values. On the other hand transform domain techniques provide more resilience by embedding data into the frequency of domain using transforms like DCT or DWT(16)

STEGANALYSIS: WHAT IT IS AND WHY IT MATTERS

The technique of uncovering information concealed within stego-object is known as steganalysis. It is steganography's opposite amd it is crucial to prevent the misuse of steganography for malicious purposes like data exfiltration or secret communication(17). Steganography techniques are developing at the same time as steganalysis techniques with the goal of efficiency identifying and combating ever-more advanced data concealment strategies. (18)

4. CLASSIFICATION OF STEGANOGRAPHIC TECHNIQUES

This section examines adaptive and intelligent approaches, analyzes steganographic techniques according to the domain in which data is is embedded (mostly spatial and transform domains), and compares performance metrics.

4.1 SPATIAL DOMAIN TECHNIQUE

Spatial-domain techniques directly manipulate pixel values of images to embed secret data

1. Least Significant bit

LSB, is one of the of the most used methods. It stores information by changing the least significant bits of pixel values. Despite being easy to use and having a large capacity, this method is extremely susceptible to steganalysis and image alteration. (19)

2. Pixel value Differencing

This method adjusts the embedding capacity according to the variation of pixel value. More data hiding can be achieved in areas with high availability, improving imperceptibility and capacity.

3. Blockchain-based spatial embedding

An innovative new approach came to life when Suresh & Kamalakannan (2023) suggested a method that uses blockchain security to embedded data without moving the stego-object (20)

4. Comparative study

In their comparative study of spatial methods Selvamani et al. (2023) found that eventhough these techniques are computationally fast and offer a large data capacity they frequently lack resilience to compression or filtering (21)

4.2 Transform domain techniques

These methods increase an images resistance to attacks by embedding information in frequency components.

1. Discrete cosine transform(DCT)

DCT-based techniques alter frequency coefficients to function. DCT and Huffman encoding were combined to improve compression and imperceptibility. (22)

2. Discreet wavelet transform (DWT)

DWT incorporates data in the wavelet coefficients to provide a multi resolution analysis. A DWT-based authentication technique was suggested by Sengupta et al. (2012) , which achieved better resistance to geometric attacks. (22)

3. FFT-based and difference expansion

Strong reversibility and robustness were demonstrated by Ding et al. (2022) when they presented scalable difference expansion in the frequency domain (23)

4.3 Adaptive and Intelligent Techniques

These techniques use artificial intelligence and optimization algorithms to embed data

- **Machine Learning & Deep Learning:**

The introduction of a cycle consistent adversarial model (GAN based) was made by Abdollahi et al. (2023) which enhanced the security and the indistinctness (25)

- **Bayesian Neural Networks:**

For his method Chang (2022) used the Bayesian networks for reversible steganography guaranteeing durability and precision.(24)

- **Optimization Algorithms:**

Algorithms like Genetic Algorithms (GA) and Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) are frequently used to maximize embedding capacity vs imperceptibility trade-offs.

- Convolutional neural networks

Convolutional neural networks and adversarial training are two learning based steganographic techniques that have gained attention recently due to their increased robustness and imperceptibility (34)

5. APPLICATIONS OF STEGANOGRAPHY

Steganography has passed from being a niche scientific and academic topic to an essential of various fields. From forensic science, digital copyright protection to military communications. These applications are what we are going to examine in this section.

5.1 Military and Confidential Communications

In military and defense applications, steganography is used to securely transmit classified information and maintain the privacy of sensitive information(30). During seasons of war, undetectable ink turned into an important device for the military, permitting messages to be sent clandestinely. (29) The artistry of hidden writing became an integral part of military strategy, a secret language shared among the known connected parties

There are proposed 2 methods that can be used in a military settings.

In this method the Advance Encryption Standard (AES) algorithm will be used in the suggested system to encrypt user-provided data. Three levels will also be provided by the suggested system. of safety. The user data will first be encrypted and then in the second step, the image will also be transformed into a QR code. Lastly the QR code will be put into video as to not to interfere with the original image ore message (26) By preventing third- party infiltration, this will reduce the need to overthink the safety of data that has been delivered. The application concentrates on enabling the defense system's most secure communication and the intuitive user interface, in contrast to other steganography platforms that prioritize app promotion over defense system security(26).

The second approach is a method for high-resolution AVI (Audio Video Interleave) films that hides and extracts data. Despite their size, AVI videos can be safely transferred from source to target over a network once they have been processed utilizing these data extraction and hiding techniques. The sender's end and the recipients end employ two distinct processes (27) encrypting and decrypting the message using a public key cryptographic algorithm, as well as embedding text in fourth and fifth layers with both the same and different data, makes more secure and reduces transparency..The systems are thought to be effective to hide messages in audio an video files so that data can reach the destination safe without being altered.

5.2 Copyright Protection and Watermarking

The digital watermarking protects the digital cover objects. A digital watermarks serves comparable tasks as electronic fingerprint. A digital watermark is a label that identifies the creator or confirms the authenticity and integrity of the digital object. Digital watermarks are often used to safeguard multimeia files, control data integrity and authenticate the source. The classic watermark is connencted with multimedia. Numerous specific algorithms are explicity apply to digital watermarking and steganography. In these cases the primary distinctions lie in the conditions necessary for data embedding to be effective(31) Three characteristics of image steganography and watermarking performance robustness, imperceptibility and capacity. Watermarking algorithms and steganographic have different purposes. Imperceptibility and the ability to effectively maintain the highest level of confidentiality are given priority in steganography. In contrast, watermarking prioritize robustness to guarantee thta the embedded data is imprevious to attacks. The capacity od data-hiding strategy to withstand different attacks or changes to the cover image without impacting the concealed data is the robustness. The degree to which the secret data is invisible to humans is the imperceptibility and the quantity of the concealed data in a particular cover image is the capacity. (39)

Despite being two different approaches, steganography and watermarking have some same characteristics. For example, both use the same model when two inputs are fed into an embedder. Additionally, both strategies use steganographic techniques to secretly embed data in noisy signals. That's why many say that steganography is digital watermarking. Multi-media types (such as video, audio, or image), human perception (such as invisibility or visibility), working domain (such as hybrid, frequency, or spatial), application type (such as destination or source-based), and algorithm type (such as parallel or sequential) are the foundations for the classification of digital watermarking techniques. (32)

There are different techniques in watermarking. In terms of the working domain, the spatial technique of watermarking is described as a technique that uses different methods like least significant bits (LSB) algorithms, patchwork algorithms and significant intermediate bits (ISB) algorithms, to insert watermark information into the host image that the owner describes within time or spatial domain. These methods are applied directly to the original pixels of an image since the watermark can be added by adjusting the pixel values, which are based on the author's signature or trademark. It can be added by adjusting the pixel values, which are based on the author's signature or trademark. Spatial watermarking is more effective, is implemented quickly, and is quite easy (32).

However, Begum and Uddin's article (37) examined how spatial domain watermarking approaches are easily manipulated and overly brittle, making them more resistant to various attack types when compared to frequency-domain algorithms. Because frequency domain watermarking techniques efficiently conceal picture data through a predefined transformation to display an image within the frequency domain, this is the reason why researchers have turned their attention to them. Then, using a variety of transforms, including the discrete Fourier transform (DFT), singular value decomposition (SVD), DWT, and DCT, the watermark is embedded by modifying the transform-domain coefficients of an image. (32) Except from the classical applications of steganography there are a few new uses of data hiding, including, among other things, network steganography, VoIP steganography, digital watermarking for forensics, digital watermarking for data provenance, privacy-preserving transaction tracking, steganography for criminals and terrorists, and steganography for malware injection. digital watermarking for forensics, digital watermarking for data provenance, privacy-preserving transaction tracking, steganography for criminals and terrorists, and steganography for malware injection. Preserving transaction tracking, steganography for criminals and terrorists, and steganography for malware injection. (38)

5.3 Digital Forensics

Digital forensics focuses on the acquisition, preservation and analysis of digital evidence.(43). In order to facilitate and advance the reconstruction of events found to be criminal or help anticipate unauthorized actions that are disruptive to planned operations , digital forensics uses scientifically derived and proven methods for the preservation, collection, validation, identification, analysis interpretation, documentation and presentation of digital evidence derived from digital sources (44). These days retrieving and analyzing already existing data on computer systems is the majority of research conducted in digital forensics. Retrieving a data from a computer system is the most crucial aspect of digital forensics.(40)

According to steganography, an unsuspected communication is covertext that becomes stegotext when a secret message is embedded. A stegosystem is the collective term for the algorithms that are used to be embedded and recover secret messages within covertext. In addition to safeguarding, it makes the stegosystem appear like covertext (41).

6. CHALLENGES AND ISSUES

Digital steganography has only been present over the past 20 years, although steganography is a very old technique that goes back roughly 2000 years. (47) People started using covert social media platforms in the last ten years. With the rise in popularity of the Internet, social media networks, which started to produce enormous amounts of information frequently. Most of the information that is generated is unimportant and neglected and people would rather disregard substantial portions of social media data. Social media steganography was developed with consideration for people's opinions. Social media users have been sending even more messages by utilizing text and image steganography but by itself it cant offer completely anonymous, it makes the secrets existence known. Even attackers may learn and try to decode it. It is important for a sender to safeguard their communication and the encryption should be used as second layer(47). Examples of well-known social media network as that are used for sharing confidential information are google+, flickr and facebook.(48)

Also existing methods are unable to keep up with contemporary steganalysis tool, quantum image steganography has been put out as strong substitute for data concealment that is future proof(35). And while there valid commercial uses for steganography like safeguarding sensitive company data while being transmitted they have become a major problem for forensic investigators and others who are worried for illicit and malevolent uses(45).Steganography technologies are becoming more accessible and user-friendly which even it is positive for the research is is easier to be used for illegal usage and the prevention is difficult(46)

Another major issue is the data loss leakage.(49) According to (50) this problem is increasing. Due to modern data transmission methods and the existing various communications networks and protocols this problem is not only increasing but also allowing the existence of hidden channels of interactions (51)

Lastly, since there are no trustworthy techniques for identifying steganography, it is thought to be too costly to protect against. Many organizations come to the conclusion that protecting against steganography is a waste of money when there is no substantiated assurance. The attacker community is making noticeable efforts to stay "ahead of the game" as the sector transitions to cloud-based services. This data suggests that the attacker community closely monitors defenders' responses and anticipates that the behavior of their real targets—naïve end users—will probably alter. (52)

7. AI AND STEGANOGRAPHY

Computers and servers have gotten better at mimicking human behavior and artificial intelligence has grown quickly in recent years, many AI has helped to tackle problems with voice recognition, image identification and natural language processing(55). Using a chain of multimodal AI, messages are incorporated in the linguistic domain of audiovisual information rather than depending on the spatial or temporal domains. While the word sample procedure is skewed towards common set of tokens the language generation model at the center of this chain is tasked with paraphrasing the provided transcript. A voice- cloning model is then used to turn the paraphrased transcript into sound and pil synchronization model is used to align the video with the audio. The correctness, secrecy, robustness, and faithfulness of the suggested steganographic system are assessed under a range of metrics and circumstances (54). The potential of AI to create realistic information is becoming a problem in the hands of cybercriminals who aim to distort and manipulate the facts as technology develops. A non-trivial risk of overwriting the steganographic alternations is introduced by such synthetic content. It is necessary to consider what if in the spatial domain and temporal domain are susceptible to unexpected overwriting (54). Depending on the author and their intent, AI generated steganography may represent exponential cybersecurity concerns.

Understanding the possible risks is crucial because the cybersecurity sector is always evolving and evolving. The cybersecurity business faces significant dangers from viruses, attacks, and other malware concealed in steganography. There will always be more issues with increasingly sophisticated technology, including attacks, attackers, and everything in between. The primary attack types that affect AI systems that generate steganography are adversarial attacks. The cycle GAN neural networks advancements make it possible for later AI devices to be more useful in the cybersecurity industry. AI devices and steganography are both excellent tools on their own, but they significantly improve cybersecurity when they are combined. Cybercriminals will continue to research and wait for the ideal moment to launch and assault as long as technology is developing (53). The potential of AI to create realistic information is becoming a problem in the hands of cybercriminals who aim to distort and manipulate facts as technology evolves seems improbable that terrorists are using digital steganography to enable covert intragroup communication, as has been asserted. This is due to the technological and practical impossibility of terrorists using digital steganography(28).

The security of papers online has also been strengthened by the addition of digital watermark to the original copy. Watermarking algorithms that apply machine learning techniques can generate and optimize the maximum likelihood relation set anticipate the optimal embedding strength speed up the training set and compromise security and resilience among other things (56).

CITATIONS

1. *Exploring steganography: Seeing the unseen*. (1998, February 1). IEEE Journals & Magazine | IEEE Xplore. <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/4655281>

2. Dickman, S. D., James Madison University Infosec Techreport, & Department of Computer Science. (2007). *An overview of steganography*.
<https://digitnet.github.io/m4jpeg/downloads/pdf/an-overview-of-steganography.pdf>
3. Petitcolas, F., Anderson, R., & Kuhn, M. (1999). Information hiding-a survey. *Proceedings of the IEEE*, 87(7), 1062–1078. <https://doi.org/10.1109/5.771065>
4. Thampi, S. M. (2008, February 26). *Information Hiding Techniques: A tutorial review*. arXiv.org. <https://arxiv.org/abs/0802.3746>
5. Goljan, M., & Westfeld, A. (2009). Secure steganography in multimedia content. *EURASIP Journal on Information Security*, 2009, 1. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2009/257131>
6. Böhme, R. (2010). Advanced Statistical Steganalysis. In *Information security and cryptography*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-14313-7>
7. Zhang, K. A., Cuesta-Infante, A., Xu, L., & Veeramachaneni, K. (2019, January 12). *SteganoGAN: High Capacity Image Steganography with GANs*. arXiv.org.
<https://arxiv.org/abs/1901.03892>
8. Xiao, C., Peng, S., Zhang, L., Wang, J., Ding, D., & Zhang, J. (2025). A transformer-based adversarial network framework for steganography. *Expert Systems With Applications*, 269, 126391. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2025.126391>
9. Xiang, X., Tan, Y., Qin, J., & Tan, Y. (2024). Advancements and challenges in coverless image steganography: A survey. *Signal Processing*, 228, 109761.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sigpro.2024.109761>

10. Luo, W., Wei, K., Li, Q., Ye, M., Tan, S., Tang, W., & Huang, J. (2024). A comprehensive survey of digital image steganography and steganalysis. *APSIPA Transactions on Signal and Information Processing*, 13(1). <https://doi.org/10.1561/116.20240038>
11. Zhang, C., Gao, X., Liu, X., Hou, W., Yang, G., Xue, T., Wang, L., & Liu, L. (2023). IDGAN: Information-Driven Generative Adversarial Network of Coverless Image Steganography. *Electronics*, 12(13), 2881. <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics12132881>
12. Li, G., Li, S., Li, M., Qian, Z., & Zhang, X. (2023, July 7). *Towards deep network steganography: from networks to networks*. arXiv.org. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2307.03444>
13. *Survey on steganography methods (text, image, audio, video, protocol and network steganography)*. (2016, March 1). IEEE Conference Publication | IEEE Xplore. <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/7724795>
14. Hussain, M., & Hussain, M. (2013). A survey of image steganography techniques. *International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology*, 54, 113-124.
15. Hussain, M., Wahab, A. W. A., Idris, Y. I. B., Ho, A. T., & Jung, K. (2018). Image steganography in spatial domain: A survey. *Signal Processing Image Communication*, 65, 46–66. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.image.2018.03.012>
16. Kabir, K. (2020). A survey on the spatial and transform domain techniques of image steganography. In *International Journal of Advances in Engineering and Management (IJAEM)* (Vols. 2–2, Issue 12, pp. 311–319). https://ijaem.net/issue_dcp/A%20Survey%20on%20the%20Spatial%20and%20Transform%20domainTechniques%20of%20Image%20Steganography.pdf

17. Shehab, D. A., & Alhaddad, M. J. (2022). Comprehensive Survey of Multimedia Steganalysis: Techniques, Evaluations, and Trends in Future research. *Symmetry*, 14(1), 117. <https://doi.org/10.3390/sym14010117>
18. Yu, J., Zhang, X., Xu, Y., & Zhang, J. (2023, May 26). *CROSS: Diffusion Model makes controllable, robust and secure image steganography*. arXiv.org. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2305.16936>
19. Almola, S. a. S. (2023). A study of image hiding techniques in the spatial domain. *Informatica*, 46(8). <https://doi.org/10.31449/inf.v46i8.4252>
20. Suresh, K. S., & Kamalakannan, T. (2023, January 27). *Digital image steganography in the spatial domain using Block-Chain technology to provide Double-Layered protection to confidential data without transferring the Stego-Object*. <https://ijisae.org/index.php/IJISAE/article/view/2508>
21. Selvamani, R., Yusoff, Y., Alwee, R., Yusuf, S. M., Yunos, Z. M., Talib, M. S., & Hasan, H. (2023). Comparative analysis of the spatial domain in digital image steganography. *Proceedings Computer Science*. <https://doi.org/10.55092/pcs2023020046>
22. Nag, A., Biswas, S., Sarkar, D., & Sarkar, P. P. (2010). A novel technique for image steganography based on Block-DCT and Huffman Encoding. *International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technology*, 2(3), 103–112. <https://doi.org/10.5121/ijcsit.2010.2308>
23. Sengupta, M., Mandal, J. K., & Ghoshal, N. (2012, December 15). *An Authentication Technique in Frequency Domain through Wavelet Transform (ATFDWT)*. arXiv.org. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1212.3719>

24. Ding, W., Zhang, H., Reulke, R., & Wang, Y. (2022). Reversible image data hiding based on scalable difference expansion. *Pattern Recognition Letters*, 159, 116–124.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patrec.2022.05.014>
25. Chang, C. (2022). Bayesian Neural Networks for reversible steganography. *IEEE Access*, 10, 36327–36334. <https://doi.org/10.1109/access.2022.3159911>
26. Abdollahi, B., Harati, A., & Taherinia, A. (2023). Image steganography based on smooth cycle-consistent adversarial learning. *Journal of Information Security and Applications*, 79, 103631. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jisa.2023.103631>
27. Shaikh, U., Singh, S., Sheth, P., & Iyer, S. (2020). Robust and secure video steganography for military communication. *Studies in Indian Place Names*, 40(35), 779–781.
<https://universalcollegeofengineering.edu.in/wp-content/uploads/2024/04/41.pdf>
28. Roy, P., & Nath, A. (2014). New Steganography approach using encrypted secret message inside Audio and Video media. *International Journal of Advance Research in Computer Science and Management Studies*, 2(12).
29. Conway, M. (2003). Code Wars: Steganography, signals intelligence, and terrorism. In *Knowledge, Technology and Policy* (Vols. 45–62) [Journal-article].
https://doras.dcu.ie/494/1/know_tech_pol_16_2_2003.pdf
30. Dangi, A. K. O., Tandon, S., Deorari, S., & Kumar, R. (2024). Steganography: Unveiling techniques and research agenda. In *IntechOpen eBooks*.
<https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.1005052>
31. *Security and Privacy Enabled Framework for Online Social Networks using Blockchain*. (2023, July 6). IEEE Conference Publication | IEEE Xplore.
<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/10193119>

32. *Digital Steganography and Watermarking for Digital Images: A Review of Current Research Directions*. (2020). IEEE Journals & Magazine | IEEE Xplore.
<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/9187785>
33. Zainal, N., Hoshi, A. R., Ismail, M., Rahem, A. a. T., & Wadi, S. M. (2024). A hybrid steganography and watermark algorithm for copyright protection by using multiple embedding approaches. *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, 13(3), 1877–1896. <https://doi.org/10.11591/eei.v13i3.6337>
34. Agrawal, R., & Ahuja, K. (2021, January 3). *CSIS: compressed sensing-based enhanced-embedding capacity image steganography scheme*. arXiv.org.
<https://arxiv.org/abs/2101.00690>
35. Hu, K., Wang, M., Ma, X., Chen, J., Wang, X., & Wang, X. (2024). Learning-based image steganography and watermarking: A survey. *Expert Systems With Applications*, 249, 123715. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2024.123715>
36. Min-Allah, N., Nagy, N., Aljabri, M., Alkharraa, M., Alqahtani, M., Alghamdi, D., Sabri, R., & Alshaikh, R. (2022). Quantum Image Steganography Schemes for Data Hiding: A survey. *Applied Sciences*, 12(20), 10294. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app122010294>
37. Babu, K. R., Kumar, S., & Babu, A. (2010). A survey on Cryptography and Steganography Methods for Information Security. *International Journal of Computer Applications*, 12(3), 13–17. <https://doi.org/10.5120/1660-2235>
38. Begum, M., & Uddin, M. S. (2020). Digital Image Watermarking Techniques: a review. *Information*, 11(2), 110. <https://doi.org/10.3390/info11020110>

39. Megías, D., Mazurczyk, W., & Kuribayashi, M. (2021). Data hiding and its applications: digital watermarking and steganography. *Applied Sciences*, *11*(22), 10928. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app112210928>
40. Hu, K., Wang, M., Ma, X., Chen, J., Wang, X., & Wang, X. (2024c). Learning-based image steganography and watermarking: A survey. *Expert Systems With Applications*, *249*, 123715. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2024.123715>
41. Castiglione, A., De Santis, A., & Soriente, C. (2006). Taking advantages of a disadvantage: Digital forensics and steganography using document metadata. *Journal of Systems and Software*, *80*(5), 750–764. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jss.2006.07.006>
42. Cachin, C. (2005). Digital Steganography.
43. Karampidis, K., Kavallieratou, E., & Papadourakis, G. (2018). A review of image steganalysis techniques for digital forensics. *Journal of Information Security and Applications*, *40*, 217–235. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jisa.2018.04.005>
44. Palmer G, A road map for digital forensic research, 2001
45. Schmidt, M. B., Bekkering, E., & Warkentin, M. (2004, April). On the illicit use of steganography and its detection. In *Proceedings of the 2004 ISOneWorld International Conference* (pp. 1-10).
46. Warkentin, M., Bekkering, E., & Schmidt, M. B. (n.d.). *Steganography: forensic, security, and legal issues*. Scholarly Commons. <https://commons.erau.edu/jdfsl/vol3/iss2/2/>
47. *Social Media and Steganography: use, risks and current status*. (2021). IEEE Journals & Magazine | IEEE Xplore. <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/9599677>
48. *The security threat posed by steganographic content on the internet*. (2007, April 1). IEEE Conference Publication | IEEE Xplore. <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/4151779>

49. Gutiérrez-Cárdenas, J. M. (2017). Steganography and Data Loss Prevention: An overlooked risk? *International Journal of Security and Its Applications*, 11(4), 71–84.
<https://doi.org/10.14257/ijisia.2017.11.4.06>
50. A. Shabtai, Y. Elovici and L. Rokach, “A survey of data leakage detection and prevention solutions”, Springer, (2012)
51. R. C. Newman, “Covert computer and network communications”, InfoSecCD '07, (2007) September, pp. 1-8.
52. Cleary, T. (n.d.). *Steganography as a threat – fairytale or fact?* Research Online.
<https://ro.ecu.edu.au/adf/148/>
53. Williams, O. C. (n.d.). *What are the cybersecurity risks of artificial intelligence generated steganography?* - ProQuest.
<https://www.proquest.com/openview/80074a5d4a72758c01c4c8fdb8a9aea/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=18750&diss=y>
54. Chang, C., & Echizen, I. (2025). Steganography beyond space-time with chain of multimodal AI. *Scientific Reports*, 15(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-97238-2>
55. *Investigating the effectiveness of artificial intelligence in watermarking and steganography for digital media security*. (2024, April 22). IEEE Conference Publication | IEEE Xplore.
<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/10549272>
- 56 *Forecasts on future evolution of artificial intelligence and intelligent systems*. (2022). IEEE Journals & Magazine | IEEE Xplore.
<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/9761872>